

The Chemistry of Jute-lignin. Part II.

Potash Fusion of Lignin.

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The structure of lignin still remains undetermined and the investigators appear to be divided mainly into three groups as to its nature. Klason (*Ber.*, 1920, **53**, 706, 1864), Heuser and Winsvold (*Cellulosechem.*, 1923, **4**, 49), Freudenberg (*Ber.*, 1929, **62**, 1554) from the chemical examination of lignin derivatives and its decomposition products hold that lignin contains the benzene nucleus together with oxidisable side chains; Herzog (*Ber.*, 1929, **62**, 1600) and Hägglund (*Svensk Kem. Tidskr.*, 1929, **41**, 185) from the study of ultraviolet absorption spectra of lignin derivatives conclude that lignin must contain at least one aromatic ring; while Strupp (*Cellulosechem.*, 1924, **5**, 6) and others consider lignin to be hydroaromatic in nature having for their support the results of pressure oxidation and vacuum distillation of lignin. The third group of workers, Willstätter and his collaborators (*Ber.*, 1922, **55**, 2637) maintain that lignin is entirely aliphatic in structure just like cellulose and pentosans with which it is closely related.

The problem has in recent years been complicated by the fact that lignins from different sources have been found to behave differently, though the same methods have been applied for their study. Powell and Whittaker (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **125**, 357) who made a thorough examination of flaxwood-lignin, observed on comparing their results with those of Cross and Bevan for jute-lignin, "Thus, jute-lignin is essentially different from flax-lignin." It appears rather unlikely that lignins from different woods have different compositions. The anomalous behaviour of lignins from different sources would just as well be explained by the degree of polymerisation. Before any definite formula can be assigned to lignin it is necessary to establish the identity of structure of the different lignins. Hence the importance of studying the decomposition products of lignins from all possible sources.

Jute-lignin was first studied as lignone chloride by Cross and Bevan (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1882, 41, 90) who assigned the formula $C_{19}H_{22}O_9$ to the "aromatic constituent" of jute-fibre. They also observed the great resemblance between jute-lignin (which they did not isolate) and catechin though they could not separate any product therefrom similar to the latter. Subsequently (*Ber.*, 1893, 26, 2520) they were struck by the yellow colour of the chloro compound of lignin similar to that of quinones from which they suggested a ketonic structure.

The large volume of experimental data obtained from the study of lignins from different woods cannot be explained by the ketonic formula unless we assume jute-lignin to be essentially different from others. Since then no work has been done on jute-lignin; the above-mentioned authors worked with lignocellulose and not with isolated lignin, and their results are difficult to interpret. Hence it was thought worth while to make a systematic study of lignin isolated from jute in order to see if it really differed from others. In an earlier paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 397) it was shown by the author that lignin extracted from jute-fibre had generally speaking almost similar properties, both physical and chemical, to some wood-lignins. In the present investigation, alkali fusion under different conditions has been studied with a view to see if it gave identical decomposition products. The results obtained confirm the view that jute-lignin is in many respects similar to, if not identical with, other lignins.

Willstätter's method has been found by the author (*loc. cit.*) to be the best for the isolation of lignin from jute, used in this investigation. The potash fusion was carried out at different temperatures, for varying times, under different atmospheres and in different vessels. Temperature has been found to be the most important factor and time the next. At temperatures above 240° only traces of protocatechuic acid and pyrocatechol could be obtained; above 260° none, whilst if the fusion was continued for more than one hour, the yield of these bodies rapidly diminished, even if the temperature was kept below 240° . Iron was shown by Heuser (*loc. cit.*) to have a catalytic effect on the potash fusion causing a higher yield of aromatic substances, while by using zinc dust Rassow and Zickmann (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1929, ii, 123, 189) was able to increase the yield of protocatechuic acid from 3 to 15%. No such improvement could be observed in the case of jute-lignin, when fused in an iron crucible in

the presence of zinc dust at temperatures specified by the authors. Obviously jute-lignin is more susceptible to the action of fused alkali than wood-lignins and is acted upon at lower temperatures. The poor yield of aromatic substances at relatively high temperatures and for prolonged times is explained by the fact that both protocatechuic acid and pyrocatechol are more or less rapidly decomposed to carbon dioxide and oxalic acid, by the oxidising action of the fused potash (Heuser and Winsvold, *loc. cit.*). The best yield of aromatic bodies was obtained by fusing jute-lignin at 220-30° for 1 hour, all the lignin being added as quickly as possible at 200°. More oxalic acid was obtained at higher temperatures but less lignic acid. No lignic acid was found at 300° when the fusion was continued for 3½ hours, oxalic acid being the only product. With wood-lignin this is not the case. With iron vessel and in an atmosphere of nitrogen only a slightly higher yield of aromatic bodies could be obtained, the maximum being 13.87%. In an atmosphere of carbon dioxide more oxalic acid was obtained but with no improvement in the yield of aromatic substances.

Butyric acid has been identified as a product of fusion of jute-lignin, the highest yield was 9.13%. No trace of vanillic acid could be detected in any of the numerous fusions carried out with jute-lignin nor any product containing any methoxy group. The formation of butyric acid indicates the presence of a side chain of at least 4 carbon atoms in the lignin molecule. Cross and Bevan's formula contains a chain but with two CO groups, which will not explain the formation of butyric acid. Again, the aromatic ring with two CO groups in 1:5 positions cannot give catechol. Lastly, protocatechuic acid has the OH groups in 3:4 positions with respect to the COOH group. In the lignin molecule the carboxyl group must have been formed by the oxidation of a side chain and the OH groups were either already present or have been formed from OCH₃ group in those positions. These do not occur in Cross and Bevan's formula, which is therefore untenable.

Hawley and Harris (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1932, 24, 873) are recently reported to have prepared lignin by heating purified wood or cellulose in sealed tubes at 138° for a maximum period of 8 days. It was similar to lignin as regards resistance to hydrolysis, chlorination, sulphide reaction, ultraviolet absorption spectrum and reducing value. They called it synthetic lignin. Jute after complete delignification by chlorine peroxide was subjected to

the same treatment, exactly under the same conditions. The white fibre turned brown and brittle. Lignin was isolated therefrom by Willstätter's method, but the brown fibre did not respond to the colour tests with aniline acetate and phloroglucinol, usually given by ordinary jute. However, the black mass, obtained after hydrolysis of the cellulose, possessed physical resemblance to genuine lignin. On fusion with potash at 220-30° in the usual way, no carbon dioxide or any other gas was evolved and no smell was perceptible. It was only partly dissolved by the alkali. On adding water, a light brown powder separated. The pale brown solution was examined for protocatechuic acid and other similar acids but none could be detected, not even oxalic acid. Thus, the so-called synthetic lignin is chemically different from genuine lignin.

Raw jute was delignified by moist chlorine peroxide gas, complete removal of lignin was ascertained by dissolving the milk-white fibre in 72% H_2SO_4 to a colourless solution. The fibre was then fused at 220-30° with caustic potash exactly in the same way as in the case of lignin. The fused mass was pale yellow and the aqueous solution gave no precipitate with dilute sulphuric acid. On steam distillation only formic and acetic acids were identified but no butyric acid. The alcoholic extract gave oxalic acid in large amounts and nothing was obtained by extraction with ether. Hence, aromatic substances are constituent parts of the lignin molecule, which must, therefore, be aromatic in nature. It is much more likely that the drastic oxidising action of fused alkali causes the decomposition of a complex molecule to simple ones, rather than the formation of aromatic bodies from aliphatic ones.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Caustic potash (25 g.), dissolved in water (10 c.c.), was heated to 200° in a large nickel crucible, provided with a nickel tube, sealed at one end or better an iron tube containing a little mercury to protect the thermometer and finely powdered lignin (5 g.) was rapidly added to the molten mass with vigorous stirring. (The lignin should be added at a temperature lower than that of fusion since the reaction is exothermic.) The mass frothed up and a pink colour developed. In order to keep the mass in the liquid state caustic potash (25 g. in 10 c.c. water) was again added after half an hour. A characteristic smell was given off during the fusion.

It is difficult to detect the end point but by repeated trials one hour has been found to be the optimum duration. At higher temperatures the mass became deep brown and finally black in which case no protocatechuic acid could be detected. At 300° for $3\frac{1}{2}$ hours a white mass was obtained giving only oxalic acid.

The mass was cooled, dissolved in the minimum quantity of water and acidified with 30% H_2SO_4 . After 2-3 hours the lignic acid separated and a clear light brown liquid was obtained by filtration. The lignic acid was washed with lukewarm water until free from H_2SO_4 , dried at 105° and weighed.

The filtrate with the washings was subjected to steam distillation, until the distillate was neutral. Butyric acid was detected in the distillate, but no phenol.

The liquid left in the distilling flask was neutralised with Na_2CO_3 and evaporated to dryness on the water-bath. The acidified dry residue was extracted with absolute alcohol in a soxhlet apparatus. After the removal of alcohol, the residue was exhaustively extracted with dry ether. The undissolved solid was treated with water, made alkaline with ammonia and oxalic acid precipitated by a boiling solution of $CaCl_2$. This was washed, dried in the steam oven and weighed.

The residue from the ether extraction was then treated with benzene in the cold. Pyrocatechol was obtained in solution while protocatechuic acid remained undissolved. The quantitative figures refer to a fusion done at $220-30^{\circ}$ in air in which 5.25 g. of lignin were taken. Results of other experiments are given in a tabular form in the next page.

Lignic acid.—1.291 G. was obtained from 5.25 g. (24.6 % of the lignin taken). It is a black amorphous solid which reduces Fehling's solution, contains no methoxy group (Zeisel), does not react with Cl_2 in aqueous suspension. It dissolves readily in alcohol but is not precipitated by ether. It contains no potassium, has 0.87% ash. A part of it was fused again at $240-60^{\circ}$ with potash in the usual way for $2\frac{1}{2}$ hours. The whole of it did not react with KOH and oxalic acid was the only product. The other part was then fused at $220-30^{\circ}$ for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours. Protocatechuic acid and oxalic acid were detected in the fused mass. Thus lignic acid appears to be the precursor of protocatechuic acid and hence of catechol.

Butyric acid.—The distillate from the steam distillation was made alkaline with Na_2CO_3 , evaporated to dryness on the water-bath

Temp.	Time.	Lignic acid.	Butyric acid.	Oxalic acid (anhydrous).	Protocatechuic acid.	Pyrocatechol.	Remarks.
280-300°	3½ hr.	Nil	Nil	20.3 %	Nil	Nil	Ni, crucible in air.
240-255°	1½	18.2%	Nil	Nil	Fe crucible, in air with zinc dust.
240-260°	1½	20.3	8.3%	...	traces	Nil	Ni vessel, in air with zinc dust.
220-230°	1	24.6	9.13	18.72	12.1%	3.5 %	Ni vessel, in air.
" "	"	"	...	17.6	13.87	3.84	Fe vessel, in N ₂ .
220-250°	"	22.0	8.7	19.2	4.7	...	Ni vessel, in air.
" "	"	20.86	4.85	...	Fe vessel, in CO ₂ .
180-200°	2	33.3	...	15.7	traces	Nil	Ni vessel, in air.
220-230°	"	23.8	9.6	2.7	Do

and the residue acidified with strong H_2SO_4 . The characteristic smell of butyric acid was at once perceptible. The mixture was then warmed cautiously with a little alcohol and the sweet pineapple odour of the butyric ester confirmed the acid. The solution of Ca-salt appeared as a precipitate on boiling. As no other acid could be detected, the acid-distillate from the fusion product in question was titrated with $N/10$ - NaOH with phenolphthalein as indicator; 53.9 c.c. of it was required, so 9.13% of butyric acid was obtained.

Oxalic acid.—The aqueous solution of the ether-insoluble residue gave a white precipitate with CaCl_2 insoluble in acetic acid and ammonia but soluble in mineral acids. It readily decolourises warm acidified KMnO_4 . The acidified solution was concentrated and kept in the vacuum desiccator, crystals of oxalic acid appeared which melted at 101° . [Found: CaO , 38.29. $\text{Ca}(\text{COO})_2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires CaO , 38.35 per cent]. The Ca-salt was dissolved in dilute H_2SO_4 and the acid estimated volumetrically with $N/10$ - KMnO_4 . 10 C. c. of the solution (made 500 c.c. from 5.25 g. lignin) required 4.35 c.c. of KMnO_4 , which corresponds to 18.72% of anhydrous oxalic acid.

Protocatechuic acid.—The residue of the ether extraction was separated by cold benzene into two fractions. The insoluble part was a light brown powder which could not be decolorised in aqueous solution with animal charcoal. It gives bluish green colour with FeCl_3 , which turns deep red with a drop of sodium carbonate solution. It turns Fehling's solution green at once and reduces slowly and it also reduces ammoniacal silver nitrate in the cold. It decolourises acid potassium permanganate rapidly and gives with lead acetate a white lead salt soluble in acetic acid. A slightly acid solution of lead acetate also precipitated the salt which was washed and dried. The finely powdered salt was suspended in ether and sulphurated hydrogen passed into it. The ethereal solution of the acid was crystallised from water, m.p. 196° (mixed m. p. with Merck's pure sample showed no depression). From 5.25 g. of lignin the residue after extraction with benzene amounted to 0.6350 g. (12.1%).

Catechol.—The pale grey residue after evaporation of benzene was decolourised and crystallised from benzene in rectangular blocks. Dried over sulphuric acid in vacuum it melted sharply at 103° . A mixed melting point with Kahlbaum's product was exactly the same. It was very easily soluble in water and it reduces neutral silver nitrate readily in the cold. It gives a green coloration with ferric

chloride and turns red with sodium carbonate solution. The aqueous solution with alkalis remains colourless. Neutral lead acetate precipitates the white lead salt which is readily soluble in acetic acid. Neutral potassium permanganate is decolourised in the cold. From 5.25 g. of lignin 0.1840 g. of catechol was obtained (3.5%).

SUMMARY.

(1) By the potash fusion of jute-lignin oxalic, butyric and protocatechuic acids, and pyrocatechol besides lignic acid have been obtained.

(2) The formation of these products proves conclusively that jute-lignin is not essentially different from various other wood-lignins.

(3) Delignified jute-fibre gave neither aromatic substances nor butyric acid when similarly treated.

(4) Cross and Bevan's formula has been shown to be untenable as it cannot explain the formation of these products.

(5) Jute-lignin has been found to be attacked at a comparatively lower temperature than wood-lignins and the best yield has been obtained at 220-30° for one hour,

(6) Lignic acid is the precursor of protocatechuic acid and so of catechol.

(7) The so-called synthetic lignin has been shown to be different from native lignin in jute.

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